

How researchers describe their data-instructions for the workshop organizer

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1. Foreword

Good research data management is the basis of successful research. It ensures the sustainability and availability of data in the long term, as well as makes it possible that the data can be reused for future science. In order for the data to be understandable, it is important to produce metadata describing the research data and documenting the research process at different stages. This ensures that the data is independently understandable and that the research process is reproducible and results verifiable.

How researchers describe their data -events were originally developed so that data support specialists across different organisations could hear how researchers describe their data in their everyday work during the research project and when it ends. Even more importantly, researchers should share good data documentation practices with each other. The purpose of this *Workshop Organizer's guide* is to inspire and help data support specialists or research communities to organize events, where researchers can share good data documentation and data description practices from peer-to-peer. The events can be held within an organization or for example disciplinary specific in cooperation with multiple organizations.

The guide contains the structure of the model event, ready-made templates for contacting researchers, an event description and registration template and a checklist of things to agree on before the event. The model event is virtual and it is planned to last two hours. However, the guide can be adapted to suit the situation or used only where appropriate. The guide can also be used as a checklist for organizing an event in general.

2. Time span for organizing the event

The templates in the time span refer to examples findable later in the text, which can be used when organizing *How researchers describe their data* -events. Otherwise, the time span can be utilized as a checklist for organizing different kind of events. Note that the same templates can be found also in the Finnish version of this publication.

When	Things to remember
2-3 months before...	<p>Developing the idea to an event</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you organize an event within the organization or do you collaborate with others? • In what language will the event be held? What language is suitable for the target group of the event? <p>Planning meetings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decide the date, time & venue of the event (online, hybrid, f2f) • Find presenters #template1 • Send a calendar invitation to presenters and organizers about the event <p>Plan the structure & schedule of the event so that you can make the registration form #template2.</p>
2 months ... to 3 weeks before	<p>Advertise the event</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share the registration form on relevant channels • Or send "save the date" as early as possible if the registration form is not complete. <p>Organize necessary planning meetings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agree on the practicalities of the occasion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who is chairing • Who is responsible for question session • Is the event recorded • Do you make notes • Remind the presenters of what is desired in the presentations as well as the duration of the speech. Also, tell about the practicalities if you have decided on them.
1-3 days before...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Send participants a reminder message about the event #template3 • Send a reminder message to the presenters if needed. • Go through the practicalities.
Event day	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meet with the presenters 15 minutes before the event starts and go through the practicalities & test screen sharing etc. • Put the recording on • Take notes if needed • Collect feedback #template4
1-5 days after...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Send a thank you message for the presenters. • Send presentation materials and the possible recording for the participants. #template5 • Write a blog post about the event, if it is relevant.

2.1. Checklist before the event

First, it is good to consider what kind of an event do you want to organize:

- Will it be an internal event within the organization or, for example, a discipline-specific event where you could collaborate with another organization's experts?
- Will the event be organized virtually, on-site (face to face) or hybrid?
- In which language will the event be held?
- How many speakers will you try to have? We recommend maximum of three speakers for a two-hour event to allow time for discussion.
- What is the structure of the event? A suggested structure for the two-hour event can be found in this guide.

Getting down to business:

- Find the presenters and tell them what kind of presentation you want them to give. Send them a calendar reservation for the event. **#template1** (templates can be found as the text progresses)
- Write an event description and create a sign-up page. **#template2**
- Create a virtual event (on Zoom/Teams) or a reserve a place for the event. If it's a hybrid event, make sure that the room has a functional sound system.
- Promote your event through relevant channels:
- Your organization's intra & email lists.
- Your partner organization's intranet & mailing lists
- Through CSC Research Data Management Competence Center "Data chat" (<https://wiki.eduuni.fi/x/1wRtCQ>), you can promote your event to data support specialist in other Finnish higher education institutions.
- Through the AVOTT calendar (<https://avointiede.fi/fi/tapahtumat>) you can get the highest visibility all over Finland.
- Send a reminder email 1-3 days before the event to those who have registered. **#template3**
- Plan how to collect feedback from the event. For example, a simple feedback form can be created in advance with the Zoom poll function **#template4**, so that it can only be launched to the participants at the end of the event.

Practicalities of running the event

- Who is the chair and keeps track of time?
- Who is responsible for the question sessions and follows the chat in a virtual event?
- Is the event recorded?
- Is someone taking notes of the event and are those notes shared to participants or are they for internal use?
- It is good practice to send a "Thank you" -message to presenters as well as all participants. At the same time you can share the event recording and materials. **#template5**

3. Event (model) structure and practicalities

The model event lasts for two hours, but the duration of the event depends on the number of speakers, the duration of the talks and the time allocated to the discussion. You can easily modify the event to meet your needs.

1. 10min Welcome & practicalities
2. 1h30min Researcher presentations (possibility for questions and discussion after each speech)
 - a. Researcher 1, 20min presentation + 10min questions and discussion
 - b. Researcher 2, 20min presentation + 10min questions and discussion
 - c. Researcher 3, 20min presentation + 10min questions and discussion
3. 20min General discussion

3.1. Things to keep in mind with practicalities

- It is a good practice that the organizers and presenters meet around 15 min before the event starts, so there is time to test screen sharing and sounds or open presentation at face-to-face events.
- If possible, the presentations should be sent to the organizer so that in case of screen-sharing problems, the organizer can share the screen.
- The chair opens the event by welcoming everyone and telling them what the event is all about (10min).
 - In the beginning, it is good to give instructions on how participants can ask questions or comment.
 - For example, in online events ask participants to keep their microphones muted and how questions can be asked (chat, raise hand). More time for discussion is reserved at the end of the event. Instructions can be shared with one or two slides during the welcome words.
- Presentations by the researchers
 - The chair gives the floor to the presenters and makes sure that the presentations are kept within the given time.
 - Researcher presentations can last for example 20min, after which 10min is reserved for questions & discussion.
 - The chairman also leads the question session after each presentation.
- At the end of the session, it is good to reserve more time for questions & discussion, about 20min.
- After the event, it is a good practice to send the participants and presenters a thank you message and, for example, a link to the recording (if the event was recorded) or public notes. At the same time, the presentation slides can be shared with the participants.

3.2. Contacting researchers who could be presenters

It is a good practice to send the speakers a calendar invitation for the event as soon as they have agreed to join.

#template1

Contacting potential presenters

We are organizing a (virtual) workshop/event about practices for describing research data.

We want to bring out concrete examples of how different disciplines document research data both during research projects and at the publication stage, so that data can be understood not only by the creators of the data, but also by others, such as the potential re-users. In addition, well-documented data and mutually agreed good data management practices will help with the onboarding of new team members and help researchers in general to remember e.g. what data that was collected five years ago means.

The aim is to dive into data management and data description through the following questions:

- How has metadata that describes the data (what the variables mean, how the data has been modified, etc.) been produced at different stages of the project? Are there any software or tools in use to describe the data (e.g. lab notebook)? Do you use readme files?
- Have you agreed on data management and data description practices in advance before starting data collection?
- Have you agreed on how to organise the data into common storage solutions?
- Do you have common file naming conventions?
- Do you use discipline-specific vocabularies, standards or ontologies to describe your data?
- What challenges have you encountered in describing or managing your data? What kind of support would you like to have from your organisation's data support services?

Data management and especially data description issues are generally perceived to be rather challenging by researchers. Furthermore, research organisations experience that there is a lack of incentives and offering training in these areas is perceived difficult since practices vary widely. However, without describing the data, it is impossible to tell afterwards how the research was carried out and to create discoverable and reusable research data. We would like to bring out different practical examples in order to increase insights and knowledge about current practices.

Would you be able to take part in our workshop by telling about your own experiences in describing research data? The presentation would be about 15-20 minutes, followed by an opportunity for questions and discussion. In particular, we would like to see some concrete, even visualisation of how you have worked with your data. This is a great opportunity to get more in-depth about your own research data and possibly get perspectives from other researchers on describing your own data, let alone getting more visibility for your research!

The event would be about two hours long and we aim to get 2-3 researchers to tell about their own experiences. The initial date proposals are: xx and xx.

Would you be interested in taking part in our workshop as a speaker and would either of the proposed dates suit you?

I'm happy to answer any further questions. Let's keep in touch!

3.3. Detailed instruction message for the speakers

A more specific instruction may include the following:

- The duration of the presentation (20min) and time for questions (10min). The presenter will share the screen themselves, but organisers can help if problems occur. At the end of the session, there is more time for discussion.
- The event can be advertise to colleagues!
- Workshop location (zoom/teams address, room/campus) in addition to the calendar invitation sent.
- What could be included in the presentation; the purpose is to discuss data management and describing data using the following questions:
 - How has metadata describing data been produced at different stages of the project (what do the variables mean, how the data has been modified, etc.)? Have software or tools been used to describe the data (e.g., a laboratory notebook)? Have you used readme-files?
 - Has the data management issues and how to document the data been agreed in advance before the data collection?
 - Has the project agreed how the data is organized in shared storage platforms?
 - Are there common file naming conventions in place?
 - Are discipline-specific vocabularies, standards, or ontologies in use to describe the data?
 - What challenges have been encountered with data documentation or managing the data? What kind of support would you like from the organization's data support services?
- It is good practice to meet 15 minutes before the event starts in Zoom/Teams or at the venue with the organizers and presenters.
 - Organizers tell the presenters how the event has been built: welcome words & instructions for asking questions (chat & raise hand at the end of the presentations).
 - Time to test screen share & audio. Presentations can be send to organizers before the start of the event.
 - Organizers can ask if the slides can be shared with the participants after the event.

3.4. Event description for the registration form

#template2

Event description for the registration form

Title: How researchers describe their data, practical experiences

- Time
- Place

Information (metadata) describing research data and documentation of the research process needs to be continuously produced through out the research project. This ensures that the data is understandable and the research process is reproducible and results verifiable. The data should be published on a trustworthy platform with sufficient metadata to make the data discoverable and reusable. Disciplines have different ways of describing data and also distinct publishing platforms, which means that mastering these requires discipline-specific expertise.

We are organizing an event (*organisation X or in cooperation with X*) where researchers (*from a specific discipline/fields*) will share how they document and describe their research data and their research process. We'll also discover why describing issues are sometimes perceived as difficult and discuss what kind of support for describing issues might be needed and is available.

Take part in our workshop in order to both hear and discuss data description practices and to get new ideas on how to document your own data so that it will be understandable years from now! This event is for people conducting research at all levels and you don't need to have done data documentation before in order to participate.

Program:

xx:xx - xx:xx 10min Welcome

xx:xx - xx:xx 1h30min Researchers' presentations (an opportunity to ask questions and to discuss after each presentation)

- Researcher 1, discipline x, 20min presentation + 10min questions and discussion
- Researcher 2, discipline x, 20min presentation + 10min questions and discussion
- Researcher 3, discipline x, 20min presentation + 10min questions and discussion

xx:xx - xx:xx 20min Final discussion

Target audience: e.g. researchers & data support personnel of research institutes

Language:

More information: the email of the organizer

3.5. Reminder message for participants

It is advisable to send a reminder 1-3 days before the event (**#template3**), usually the previous day is the most effective.

#template3

Event reminder for participants

Hey!

Thank you for registering for our event!

The name of the event:

Time:

Participation link:

Best regards,

The organizing team

3.6. Feedback and thank you

Remember to collect feedback after the event (**#template4**). You get the best response percentage when you ask for feedback right at the end of the event, e.g. with the zoom poll function.

#template4

Feedback survey e.g. Zoom-poll at the end of the event

1. Did the event meet your expectations 1=badly 2=moderately 3=I don't know 4=yes 5=excellently
2. Development ideas in terms of the event:
3. Wishes for the future

After the event, it is good practice to send a thank-you email to both speakers and participants (**#template5**). In the same message, participants can, for example, be given the presentation slides or link to the recording.

#template5

Thank you message for the participants

Hi!

Thank you for participating in the "xxx" event!

The *recording* of the event will be available for viewing *for two weeks*. The *slides* are also available for download.

Best regards, Organizers

4. In the end

When the event has been held, it would be beneficial to write down the good data documentation practices or discipline-specific methods that emerged. Consequently, it is easier to share good practices either within the organization, in the research community or to other colleagues in different organizations. The more good practices and examples can be shared, the more the knowledge of describing data will grow and probably even more good practices can be created!

Although this *Organizer's guide* has detailed information on organizing this model event, you can freely apply this guide as you wish to suit your own needs.